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& IQTISODIYOT

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- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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MUNDARIJA

KORXONALARDA ICHKI AUDIT TIZIMINING BOSHQARUV QARORLARI QABUL QILISHDAGI O'RNINI	24
Mexmonaliyev Ulug'bek Erkinjon o'g'li	
FISKAL SIYOSAT SAMARADORLIGI VA SOLIQ TUSHUMLARI DINAMIKASI: O'ZBEKISTON MISOLIDA ILMIY TAHLIL	30
Abduraimova Nigora Abdugapparovna	
YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI KELTIRIB CHIQUARUVCHI ASOSIY OMILLAR HAMDA IQTISODIYOTGA TA'SIRI	37
Toxtabayev Oybek Odilovich	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATI KORXONALARIDA ZAMONAVIY BOSHQARUV	42
Rasulova Muxabbat Teshabayevna, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON GLOBAL-IQTISODIY RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING O'RNINI	48
Kuvatova Oliya Sheraliyevna	
QURILISH SANOATIDA KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINING IQTISODIY MOHIYATI VA ULARNI KAPITAL BOZORI INSTRUMENTLARI ORQALI MOLIALASHTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	54
Igitov Jurabek Kuzibekovich	
IQTISODIY ISLOHOTLAR DAVRIDA TIJORAT BANKLARINING INVESTITSIYA FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING OMILLARI	61
Yangiboyev F.B.	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA MUAMMOLI KREDITLARNI ERTA ANIQLASH VA BOSHQARISHNING INTEGRATSIYALASHGAN RISK-INDEKS MODELINI	68
Kalandarov Abdulla Baxtiyorovich, Rajabov Shoxrux Suvon o'g'li	
RUX VA QO'RG'OSHINNI SELEKTIV AJRATIB OLISHNI KOMBINATSIYALASH TEXNOLOGIYASI VA NAZARIYASI.....	74
Eshonqulov Uchqun Xudaynazar o'g'li, Haqberdiyev Dilshod Qodir o'g'li	
UY-JOY QURILISHI HAJMINI UZOQ MUDDATLI PROGNOZLASHDA EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH USULLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	81
Qidirniyazov Ajiniyaz Sherniyazovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BOG'DORCHILIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA IQLIM VA TABIIY OFATLAR NATIJASIDA YETKAZILDAN TALOFATLARNI DAVLAT TOMONIDAN KOMPENSATSIYA QILISH MEKANIZMI.....	85
Sattorov Orifjon Boymurodovich	
AHOLI MOLIVAVIY SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH ORQALI YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI QISQARTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	90
Abdug'aniyev Uchqun Habibulla o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON QURILISH SANOATIDA KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINING RIVOJLANISH DINAMIKASI VA TENDENSIYALARI	96
Musaeva Aynura Abayxolievna	
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SOCIAL INFRASTRUCTURE TRANSFORMATION IN THE CONTEMPORARY ENVIRONMENT.....	104
Normurodov Khusan Eshmakhmatovich	
AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARINING INVESTITSION FAOLLIGINI BAHOLASH YO'LLARI	108
Begamov S.X.	
DEBITORLIK QARZLARINING STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV HISOBINI TASHKIL QILISH YO'NALISHLARI	112
Normatova Gulmira Xayrullaevna	

SOLIQLARNI PROGNOZLASH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH AMALIYOTI TAHLILI.....	118
Ergashov Jamshid Ashurovich	
MEHNAT XARAJATLARI HISOB: NAZARIY ASOSLAR, USULLAR VA BOSHQARUVDA AHAMIYATI.....	126
Tulyaganov Abdumalik Abdiraximovich	
KORPORATIV XIZMATLARNING BANK FOYDASIGA TA'SIRI: KOMISSION VA FOIZLI DAROMADLAR TAHLILI	131
Qurbonov Abror Abdullayevich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA MUAMMOLI KREDITLARNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING INSTITUTSIONAL VA TASHKILY MEXANIZMLARI.....	136
Djamalov G'ofir Oribjanovich	
OCHIQLIK INDEKSI VA KORRUPSIYAGA QARSHI KURASH SAMARADORLIGI: O'ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASINING INSTITUTSIONAL TAHLILI	144
Diilshod Pulatov, Uchqun Abdug'aniyev	
DUNYO SUG'URTA KOMPANIYALARINING MOLIVAVIY HOLATI VA NATIJALARI TAHLILI.....	153
Alimov Baxodir Batirovich	
QISHLOQ HUDUDLARIDA XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	160
Yuldashova Nilufar Ziyabayevna	
QURILISH TASHKILOTLARIDA BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING INNOVATSION USULLARI	164
Muxibova Guli Yarkinovna, Sharifxodjayeva Odina Ulug'bek qizi	
AXBOROT-RESURS MARKAZLARINING TA'LIM JARAYONIGA TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH.....	168
Pirmedova Xayitgul Muxammedovna	
IJTIMOYIY HIMOYA QAMROVINI KENGAYTIRISH MEXANIZMLARI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA INSTITUSIONAL YONDASHUVLAR.....	173
Bafoyev Farrux Jo'raqulovich	
KORXONALARDA AI-DRIVEN "DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEMS" (DSS)NI JORIY ETISHNING KONSEPTUAL ASOSLARI	181
Mardanova Ra'no	
STRENGTHENING THE FINANCING OF FAMILY-OWNED ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN THROUGH BANK CREDIT	186
Baymuratova Zina Aqilbekovna, Ibadullaeva Asal Ulugbek qizi	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA DAVLAT BOSHQARUV TIZIMLARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH	192
Aytmuratov Qutlimurat Jalgasovich	
ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS FROM FINANCIAL MARKETS AND FACTORS INFLUENCING THE INCREASE OF THEIR ATTRACTIVENESS	196
Kholov Sherali Akhrorboyevich	
MARKAZIY OSIYODA TRANSCHEGARAVIY SUV RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISH VA ADOLATLI TAQSIMLASHNING NAZARIY-HUQUQIY ASOSLARI.....	200
Matkarimov Mansur	
XALQARO XIZMATLAR SAVDOSIDA TIBBIY TURIZMNING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI.....	206
Farxodova Shohnoz Umidbek qizi	
BANK XIZMATLARI SIFATINI BAHOLASHNING KO'P OMILLI INDIKATORLARI TIZIMI	213
Ibroximov Iloxomjon Shavkatjon o'g'li	
SANOAT KORXONALARINI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	219
Tillayeva Barno Ramiztdinovna	
NOTIJORAT TASHKILOTLAR FAOLIYATIDA AUDITORLIK TEKSHIRUVI VA AUDITORLIK HISOBOTLARINING O'ZIGA XOSLIGI.....	224
Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich, Ubaydullayev Toxirjon Abdullajanovich	

ЦИФРОВЫЕ ИНСТРУМЕНТЫ РЕИНТЕГРАЦИИ ВОЗВРАЩАЮЩИХСЯ ТРУДОВЫХ МИГРАНТОВ: МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ ПРАКТИКА И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ДЛЯ КЫРГЫЗСТАНА.....	230
<i>Амантурова Дилбара Кыдыкбековна</i>	
РОЛЬ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНО-ОРИЕНТИРОВАННОЙ ЛЕКСИКИ В ЯЗЫКОВОЙ ПОДГОТОВКЕ ИНОСТРАННЫХ СТУДЕНТОВ ТЕХНИЧЕСКОГО ПРОФИЛЯ.....	237
<i>Асрарова М.У.</i>	
О СКОРИНГОВЫХ МЕТОДАХ ЭКСПРЕСС-АНАЛИЗА ДОХОДНОСТИ АКЦИЙ УЗБЕКСКИХ ЭМИТЕНТОВ.....	242
<i>Ирмухамедова Муслима Дилшодовна</i>	
UY-JOY QURILISHIDA ESKROU MEKANIZMLARINI JORIY ETISH ORQALI INVESTITSION XAVFSIZLIK VA MOLIVAVIY SHAFFOFLIKNI TA'MINLASH	247
<i>Karimov Inomjon Ortikbaevich</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA KICHIK BIZNESNING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI	254
<i>Kamoliddinov Ilhomjon Muxammadjonovich, Kobilov Murod Vakkosovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINING MOLIVAVIY BARQARORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARIGA TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH.....	259
<i>Axmedov Toxirjon Xasanjon o'g'li</i>	
SANOAT KORXONALARI IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA ENERGETIKA VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH SALOHİYATINING ROLI	264
<i>Tursunxo'jayev Sardor Jamoliddin o'g'li</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KOMPLAENS-NAZORAT TIZIMI ORQALI RISKLARNI SAMARALI BOSHQARISH	270
<i>Fayziyev Sherzod Djunaydilloyevich</i>	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ БАНКОВСКИМИ РИСКАМИ И СТРАХОВАНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫХ ОПЕРАЦИЙ В УСЛОВИЯХ РАЗВИТИЯ ДИСТАНЦИОННОГО БАНКИНГА В ХОРЕЗМСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ.....	275
<i>Бахтиёров Худайберган Хамдам угли</i>	
DOIMIY BO'LMAGAN KUCH TA'SIRIDA DEFORMATSIYALANUVCHAN STANDART CHIZIQLI QATTIQ MODEL ISHLAB CHIQRISH VA SONLI TAHLIL QILISH.....	282
<i>Ahmadov Ilhom Aktam o'g'li, Isomova Sabohat Islom qizi</i>	
YOUTH ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A FACTOR OF STRUCTURAL ECONOMIC TRANSFORMATION IN UZBEKISTAN.....	290
<i>Isakjanova Saboxat Muhamedovna</i>	
МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ САМОВОЗБУЖДЕНИЕ НЕЯВНОПОЛЮСНОГО СИНХРОННОГО ГЕНЕРАТОРА ПРОДОЛЬНО-ПОПЕРЕЧНОГО ВОЗБУЖДЕНИЯ	298
<i>Пирматов Нурали Бердиёрович, Бекишев Аллаберген Ергашевич, Бердиёров Улугбек Нурали угли, Бердиёров Улмасбек Нурали угли</i>	
YURTIMIZDAGI EKOLOGIK SOF YOG'OCH MATERIALLARIDAN TAYYORLANGAN ORAYOPMA KONSTRUKSIYALARINING CHO'ZILISHGA QARSHILIGI	305
<i>Yunusaliyev Elmurod Muhammadyaqubovich, Toshpulatov Ilhomjon Baxtiyorovich</i>	
AYDAR-ARNASOY KO'LLAR TIZIMINING SHAKLLANISH BOSQICHLARI VA ZAMONAVIY EKOLOGIK MUAMMOLARI	311
<i>Aminov Hamza Husanovich, Madrimov Rajabboy Masharipovich, Xamdullayeva Aziza Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
EXPLAINABLE AI YORDAMIDA SOC UCHUN TUSHUNTIRILADIGAN KIBERXAVF ANIQLASH TIZIMINI ISHLAB CHIQRISH	318
<i>N.N. Jo'rayev, A.Sh. Juraboyev</i>	
QUYOSH FOTOELEKTRIK MODULLARINI SUV YORDAMIDA TOZALASH VA SOVITISH USULLARI TAHLILI	324
<i>Ibragimov Umidjon Hikmatullayevich, Qodirov Jobir Ro'zimatovich, Izomov Shahzod Niyoz o'g'li, To'yurodov Quvonchbek Sherzod o'g'li</i>	

RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING QURILISH SOHASIGA INTEGRATSIYASI: ILG'OR XALQARO TAJRIBA	332
<i>Fayziyeva Gulnoza Abdurahmonovna</i>	
ФАКТОРЫ НАЛОГОВОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ И ИХ ВЛИЯНИЕ НА СОБИРАЕМОСТЬ НАЛОГОВ: СОЦИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ И ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ	339
<i>Хакимова Ситора Ильёсжон кизи, Муталова Дилором Махамаджановна</i>	
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ЭКСПЕРТНОГО ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЯ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ В ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ	345
<i>Л.А. Кадырова, Б. Н. Эгамов</i>	
О'ЗБЕКISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA SUG'URTA BOZORINING TUZILISHI TAHLILI	350
<i>G'oziyeva Aziza Abdusalomovna</i>	
MINTAQALARDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH MANBALARINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISH MASALALARI	358
<i>Xamrayev Quvvat Iskandarovich</i>	
KONTEYNERLI TASHUVLARNING JORIY HOLATI, MAVJUD MUAMMOLAR VA RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	366
<i>Samatov G'affor Alloqulovich, Xolmatov Bekzod Nurmatovich, Toxirov Maxmudjon Murodjon o'g'li, Absattarov Isomiddin Xotam o'g'li</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES KORXONALARIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH OMILLARI BO'YICHA NOMUVOFIQLIKNI ANIQLASH VA BARTARAF ETISH MEXANIZMI	381
<i>Kaypnazarova Gulshad Xojamuratovna</i>	
TASHQI SAVDO BALANSINI MUVOZANATLASHTIRISH: NAZARIY VA AMALIY JIHATLAR	386
<i>Rahimov Eshmurod Normurodovich, Misliiddinov Ikromjon Kamoliddin o'g'li</i>	
SIFATLI TIBBIY XIZMAT KO'RSATISH VA AHOLIGA QAMROVNI TA'MINLASHDA BOSHQARUV QARORLARINING AHAMIYATI	391
<i>Satvoldiyev Ulugbek Kamilovich</i>	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT TIZIMLARIDA GIPERPARAMETRLARNI MATEMATIK OPTIMALLASHTIRISH USULLARI	396
<i>Husan Arziqulov Normurod o'g'li</i>	
ENHANCING THE SERVICE SECTOR AS A MEANS OF CREATING EMPLOYMENT IN TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE	401
<i>Zarikeev Rasul Polatovich</i>	
EXPANDING BANK CREDIT OPPORTUNITIES FOR FAMILY-OWNED ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN	406
<i>Isakov Janabay Yakipbaevich</i>	
BANKS' BROKERAGE AND ADVISORY SERVICES IN FACILITATING SECURITIES TRANSACTIONS AND IMPROVING MARKET LIQUIDITY	412
<i>Isakov Isobek Janabay uli</i>	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ МЕХАНИЗМОВ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ ВНЕШНЕЙ ТОРГОВЛИ	416
<i>Ибрагимов Мансур Ахметович</i>	
ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ЛОГИСТИЧЕСКИХ ПРОВАЙДЕРОВ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПОСТРОЕНИЯ НОВЫХ ЦЕПЕЙ ПОСТАВОК	421
<i>Маннапова Феруза Фахриддин кызы</i>	
О'ЗБЕКISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA ISLOM MOLIYASINI HUQUQIY TARTIBGA SOLISH VA INSTITUSIONAL ASOSLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	428
<i>Isroilov Obid Olimjonovich</i>	
OZIQ-OVQAT BOZORI KON'YUNKTURASINI BAHOLASHDA KO'P OMILLI REGRESSIYA MODELINING SAMARADORLIGI	433
<i>Abduraxmonov Adxamjon Sultonboyevich</i>	

AHOLI TURMUSH TARZINI YAXSHILASHNING ISTIQBOLLARI.....	438
Djuraeva Didora Sobirjonovna	
ZAMONAVIY MOLIVAVIY INFRATUZILMANING INSTITUSIONAL ASOSLARI: TO'LOV TIZIMLARI NAZARIYASI VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI	441
Toshniyozov Sherali Kamoliddinovich	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI MENEJMENT VA SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA STRATEGIK BOSHQARUVNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	449
Zayavitdinova Nafisa Muxammadovna	
CORPORATE GOVERNANCE, FDI, AND URBANIZATION IN THE GREEN ECONOMIC TRANSFORMATION OF UZBEKISTAN	454
Ablaeva Valentina	
FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND MICRO-ENTERPRISE DEVELOPMENT	460
Dilafuz Kuchkorova	
LEGIRLANGAN PO'LATLARDAN TAYYORLANGAN PROKATLASH JO'VALARINI CHIDAMLILIGINI OSHIRISH UCHUN TERMIK PUXTALASH TEXNOLOGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	466
Saydumarov Botir Muradovich, Berdiyev Darob Murotovich, Tashmatov Ravshan Qobilovich	
SHAMOL TURBINASINING IKKI TOMONLAMA TA'MINLANADIGAN ASINXRON GENERATORI O'TKINCHI JARAYONLARINING TAHLILI	471
Bekishev Allabergen Yergashevich, Kurbonov Najmiddin Abduxamidovich, Yunusov Obidxon Abdivait o'g'li, Jo'rayev Doston Majid o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLAR FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHGA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI.....	479
Babaxanova Dildora Rustamovna	
RAQOBAT USTUNLIGIGA ERISHISHDA ZAMONAVIY MARKETING TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO'LLASH	485
Meliqulov Abduhalil Norinovich	
JAMOAT AHAMIYATIGA EGA TASHKILOTLAR TOIFASIGA KIRITISH MEZONLARI, ULARNING MOLIVAVIY HISOBOTLARI VA AUDITIGA QO'YILADIGAN TALABLAR.....	490
Shodiyev Murodjon Bakirovich	
EFFICIENCY OF IMPROVING THE IT SERVICES EXPORT	494
Uzakov Ortik Shaymardanovich	

EFFICIENCY OF IMPROVING THE IT SERVICES EXPORT

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Abstract. Export of IT services is of great importance for countries. Its development contributes to economic growth and competitiveness, and its effectiveness depends on many internal and external factors. State support mechanisms play an important role in this process. In the development of exports, financial incentives, tax incentives, infrastructure creation, personnel training, and access to global markets are considered. IT allows companies to expand export activities, create competitive services, and ensure sustainable growth in international markets. It also focuses on issues such as transparency and optimal allocation of resources, justifying its role in diversifying the economy.

Keywords: IT services export, digital economy, export development, financial incentives, tax breaks, infrastructure creation, training, global markets, efficiency, transparency, competitiveness.

Annotatsiya. IT-xizmatlar eksporti mamlakatlar uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, uning rivojlanishi iqtisodiy o'sish va raqobatbardoshlikni oshirishga xizmat qiladi hamda uning samaradorligi ko'plab ichki va tashqi omillarga bog'liq bo'lib, davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlari bu jarayonda muhim rol o'ynaydi. IT-xizmatlar eksportini rivojlantirishda moliyaviy rag'batlar, soliq imtiyozlari, infratuzilma yaratish, kadrlar tayyorlash va global bozorlarga chiqish yo'nalishlari ko'rib chiqiladi. IT kompaniyalarda eksport faoliyatini kengaytirish, raqobatbardosh xizmatlar yaratish va xalqaro bozorlarda barqaror o'sishni ta'minlash imkonini beradi hamda shaffoflik va resurslarni optimal taqsimlash kabi muammolarga e'tibor qaratish, iqtisodiyotni diversifikatsiyalashdagi rolini asoslaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: IT-xizmatlar eksporti, raqamli iqtisodiyot, eksportni rivojlantirish, moliyaviy rag'batlar, soliq imtiyozlari, infratuzilma yaratish, kadrlar tayyorlash, global bozorlar, samaradorlik, shaffoflik, raqobatbardoshlik.

Аннотация. Экспорт ИТ-услуг имеет огромное значение для стран. Его развитие способствует экономическому росту и конкурентоспособности, а его эффективность зависит от множества внутренних и внешних факторов. При этом важную роль в данном процессе играют механизмы государственной поддержки. При развитии экспорта учитываются финансовые стимулы, налоговые льготы, создание инфраструктуры, подготовка кадров и доступ к мировым рынкам. ИТ позволяют компаниям расширять экспортную деятельность, создавать конкурентоспособные услуги и обеспечивать устойчивый рост на международных рынках. Они также фокусируются на таких вопросах, как прозрачность и оптимальное распределение ресурсов, оправдывая свою роль в диверсификации экономики.

Ключевые слова: экспорт ИТ-услуг, цифровая экономика, развитие экспорта, финансовые стимулы, налоговые льготы, создание инфраструктуры, обучение, глобальные рынки, эффективность, прозрачность, конкурентоспособность.

INTRODUCTION

Against the backdrop of the rapid development of the digital economy, the export of IT services is gaining importance for countries. This sector not only stimulates economic growth but also allows for increasing national competitiveness and ensuring effective integration with global markets. At the same time, the effectiveness of the export of IT services depends on many internal and external factors, in particular the support mechanisms provided by the state, which play an important role in the sustainable development of the sector and the creation of competitive services.

Government support measures such as financial incentives, tax breaks, infrastructure development, training of skilled personnel, and assistance in entering international markets enable companies to expand

their export activities, create innovative services, and ensure sustainable growth. Therefore, the strategic importance of improving government mechanisms in developing the IT services export network is significant.

It is important to analyze the effectiveness of state support mechanisms in developing the export of IT services, to identify their strategic role, and to study the problems that arise in their implementation. The results of the study will make a practical contribution to improving state policy and increasing export potential in the context of the digital economy.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The impact of the digital economy on export processes has been widely covered in foreign and domestic scientific research. In particular, P. Krugman and M. Obstfeld, in their studies, substantiate the impact of foreign trade on economic growth and emphasize the strategic importance of digital technologies in global competition. M. Porter's concept of "National Competitive Advantage" also considers digital innovations as an important factor in increasing export competitiveness [1, 2].

Local researcher Hasanov B., in his scientific work, analyzes the institutional foundations of the export system of Uzbekistan and notes that the development of logistics infrastructure serves to further increase export potential [3]. Research conducted by Yuldashev Sh. highlights the effectiveness of digital export mechanisms and the positive impact of financial and institutional support measures provided by the state. Hasanov B. also justifies the need to expand existing opportunities in the process of digitalization of logistics infrastructure.

According to the World Bank, the use of digital trade platforms in developing countries can significantly simplify export processes and reduce costs by 30–40%. In the process of preparing this article, analytical and statistical methods were used, based on official data on export indicators from the National Statistics Committee and the Chamber of Commerce and Industry. In addition, the activities of large exporting business entities were studied in practice [4].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article used the following research methods in a comprehensive manner:

- analytical approach – systematic study of state policy and regulatory legal documents;
- statistical analysis – assessment of the dynamics of export indicators based on data from official government bodies;
- comparative method – comparing the advantages and effectiveness of traditional and digital export mechanisms;
- practical observation – direct study and generalization of the activities of exporting business entities.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The importance of state support mechanisms. The IT services export sector is an important component of the digital economy of strategic importance. Its sustainable development will not only accelerate the country's economic growth but also increase national competitiveness, strengthen innovative potential, and ensure effective integration into the global economic space. The successful operation of this sector depends on many internal and external factors, and the support mechanisms formed by the state play a decisive strategic role in the harmonious and effective functioning of these factors.

One of the main and priority areas of state support is financial incentive mechanisms. Forms of financial support, including grants, subsidies, soft loans, and tax preferences, create favorable conditions for IT companies to launch new projects, develop innovative services, and expand the range of existing services. Such financial instruments serve to increase export potential, strengthen the investment activity of companies, and expand their long-term strategic planning capabilities [5].

The second important area of state support is the formation of institutional and regulatory infrastructure. This infrastructure serves to create a favorable business environment for entities engaged in the export of IT services, reduce administrative barriers, and simplify the processes of entering foreign markets. At the same time, a regulatory framework that meets international standards will allow companies to produce high-quality and competitive services. Through a systematic and strategic approach of the state, IT companies will have the opportunity to introduce innovative solutions that meet the requirements of the global market.

The third area is related to the impact of state support mechanisms on increasing the capacity of companies and expanding export volumes. An effective support system allows for the rational use of resources, optimization of operating costs, and modernization of production and service processes. As a result, IT companies will have the ability to offer competitive services not only in the domestic market but also internationally.

At the same time, the strategic importance of state support mechanisms allows companies to reduce various economic and technological risks and ensure sustainable development. They are provided with the necessary resources to make quick and flexible decisions in the face of global economic instability, increased competition, or technological transformations. As a result, the long-term and sustainable development of the IT services export network is ensured, and the country's position in the digital economy is further strengthened [6].

Infrastructure and training. The effectiveness of IT services exports is not limited to financial support but also directly depends on the availability of modern technological infrastructure and the level of development of the system for training highly qualified personnel. IT parks, technological hubs, incubation and training centers established by the state play an important role in creating a favorable innovative environment for companies, developing services based on advanced technologies, optimizing production processes, and offering products and services that fully comply with international standards.

These infrastructure facilities will expand the opportunities for IT companies to centralize technological resources, actively support research and development (R&D), and introduce new business models and digital services. As a result, companies will be able to increase their innovative potential and gain a competitive position in foreign markets.

At the same time, state programs aimed at training qualified personnel and continuously developing their professional competencies are a decisive factor in improving the quality of exported IT services. Such programs form the digital literacy of specialists, skills in working with advanced technologies, and the ability to create services that meet the requirements of the global market. Highly qualified personnel serve not only to improve technological processes but also to ensure the strategic development of companies, accelerate innovative activities, and strengthen international competitiveness [7].

Support in entering global markets. Support mechanisms provided by the state are an important strategic resource that ensures the successful entry of IT companies into international markets. These mechanisms are multifaceted in their content and include measures aimed at marketing and promoting the national IT brand, financing trade missions and participation in international exhibitions and forums, institutional simplification of export processes, as well as optimization of costs associated with logistics and foreign economic activity.

State programs aimed at marketing and brand development allow IT companies to systematically promote their services in global markets, increasing their international recognition and competitiveness. Trade missions and participation in prestigious international exhibitions and fairs allow companies to attract new business partners, expand their portfolio of export contracts, and conduct an in-depth study of market requirements in different regions. These state-funded initiatives serve to diversify the geography of exports and capture promising market segments, ensuring sustainable growth in export volumes.

In addition, state support mechanisms encourage IT companies to develop products and services that meet international standards and have high added value. In this process, the introduction of quality management systems, technological modernization, and the use of innovative solutions strengthen the competitive advantages of companies in the global market. As a result, these mechanisms serve not only to increase the profits and market share of companies but also to enhance the country's international position in the digital economy [8].

At the same time, the state's strategic and comprehensive approach is of great importance in ensuring the security and efficiency of export activities. It prepares IT companies for flexible and sustainable operation in the face of external economic shocks, exchange rate fluctuations, and increased global competition. As a result, the long-term sustainable development of the IT services export sector is ensured, and its potential is fully realized [9] (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Improving state support mechanisms for developing the export of IT services

In the current digital economy, improving state support mechanisms for developing IT services exports is an important strategic task. The main areas for improving these mechanisms include several interrelated components (Figure 1).

First direction – efficient allocation of resources and increased transparency. Efficiently allocated resources increase the ability of companies to implement projects, effectively use budget funds, and create a stable anti-corruption mechanism. Ensuring transparency strengthens trust between companies and government agencies, ensuring fairness and consistency in the support process.

Second direction – aligning financial incentives and tax breaks with the potential of exported services. This approach will direct companies to high-potential projects, encourage the creation of innovative services, and expand investment opportunities. At the same time, aligning tax breaks will allow companies to make long-term strategic plans and increase export volumes [10].

Third direction – expanding technological infrastructure and supporting innovative startups. Modern IT parks, technology hubs, and innovation centers will help startups and companies centralize technological resources, expand research and development activities, and introduce new products and services. This will allow companies to offer services that meet global standards.

Fourth direction – training qualified personnel and ensuring their compliance with global standards. Qualified personnel increase the company's innovative and technological potential, form the ability to create services that meet the requirements of the global market, and guarantee the quality of exported services. Qualified personnel serve not only the development of technological processes but also strategic development and strengthening of competitiveness [11].

Fifth direction – development of international cooperation and integration with markets. State support serves as a strategic resource for companies to enter international markets, establish partnerships, and expand export activities. In this way, companies will have the opportunity to capture new market segments, increase export volumes, and ensure competitiveness in the global arena.

In general, these areas are an important strategic basis for increasing the effectiveness of state support mechanisms in developing the IT services export network and diversifying the digital economy.

The analysis shows that effective state support mechanisms serve as a key strategic factor in the development of the IT services export industry. These mechanisms allow companies to increase export volumes, create competitive services, and ensure sustainable development. At the same time, state support encourages companies to introduce innovative solutions, modernize technological infrastructure, and strengthen their positions in global markets.

The results of the analysis show that when implementing support mechanisms, it is necessary to pay attention to several important factors:

ensuring transparency – which strengthens trust between the state and companies and guarantees the efficient use of resources.

optimal allocation of resources – increases the capacity of companies to implement projects and directs them towards high-potential services.

focus on strategic directions – encourages companies to create innovative solutions that meet the demands of the global market in the digital economy [12].

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Improving state support mechanisms will serve not only at the company level but also to increase the digital diversification and global competitiveness of the national economy. In the long term, an effective support system will expand the global potential of the IT services export network, create opportunities for capturing new market segments, and contribute to strengthening the country's position in the digital economy.

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